

External entropy supply for IoT devices employing a RISC-V Trusted Execution Environment

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Abstract. Entropy—a measure of randomness—is compulsory for the generation of secure cryptographic keys; however, Internet of Things (IoT) devices that are small or constrained often struggle to collect sufficient entropy. In this article, we solve the entropy provisioning problem for a fleet of IoT devices that can generate a limited amount of entropy. We employ a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) based on RISC-V to create an external entropy service for a fleet of IoT devices. A small measure of true entropy or pre-installed keys can establish initial secure communication. Once connected, devices can request cryptographically strong entropy from a TEE-backed server. RISC-V offers True Random Number Generators (TRNGs) and a TEE for devices to attest that they are receiving reliable entropy. In addition, this solution can be expanded by adding IoT devices with sensors that produce high-quality entropy as additional entropy sources for the RISC-V entropy provider. Our open-source implementation shows that building trusted entropy infrastructure for IoT is both feasible and effective on open RISC-V platforms.

Keywords: RISC-V hardware · Entropy · Randomness · Trusted Execution Environment · Cryptography · Network protocols · IoT

1 Introduction

Entropy—a measure of randomness—is compulsory for the generation of secure cryptographic keys. Small or resource-constrained Internet of Things (IoT) devices often struggle to collect sufficient high-quality entropy for secure cryptographic operations. When constrained devices experience entropy starvation, it can result in predictable cryptographic outputs that undermine the security of keys and communications.

Previously, this problem was solved with (i) True Random Number Generators (TRNGs), which use inherently random physical processes like electronic noise or photonic processes to provide a built-in entropy source, which is usually part of the device’s main processor; (ii) Hybrid Entropy Sources, which use

both software (pseudo-random) and hardware (true random) sources to produce random values; and (iii) Environmental Sources, which use IoT sensors, such as temperature, light, and motion sensors, can serve as sources of entropy if their readings are unpredictable; instability from oscillators or clock drift can also be a source of entropy. User interaction, i.e., a user touching buttons or moving the device as a source of entropy, is an extension of this concept.

However, it is important to take precautions to prevent adversaries from easily manipulating environmental data. If these options are unavailable or provide a limited amount of entropy, techniques such as whitening algorithms [1] can be used to derive longer keys from lower-entropy sources. Furthermore—using extractors such as cryptographic hash functions or key derivation functions—a small quantity of entropy that is available as a seed can be used to generate a larger, deterministic, but pseudo-random value [15, 19, 11]. However, these techniques may be computationally intensive for devices with limited resources.

Another option is to provide unique device certificates during manufacturing or configuration, but even if an IoT device begins with a strong key, that key must be periodically regenerated or re-seeded with new entropy to maintain security.

In this article, we solve the problem of entropy provisioning for a fleet of IoT devices that can generate a limited amount of entropy: A Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) based on RISC-V provides entropy for a fleet of devices. Initial secure communication can be established with a small measure of true entropy or with pre-installed keys. After establishing the channel, devices receive entropy from a reliable external source. RISC-V-based Secure Platform for ICT Systems Rooted at the Silicon Manufacturing Process (SPIRS) project provides TRNGs and TEE mechanisms for devices to attest to the provision of entropy. In addition, this solution can be expanded by adding IoT devices with sensors that produce entropy as additional entropy sources for the RISC-V entropy provider. TEE is used to enable a design with no Trusted Third Party (TTP) in our Entropy as a Service (EaaS) protocol.

We make the following novel contributions in this paper: (i) We design, develop, and publish a SPIRS TEE software development kit (SDK) that enables the development of Trusted Applications (TAs) for the RISC-V-based SPIRS platform—allowing open-source development of TAs for a RISC-V-based TEE. (ii) We design, develop, and publish an EaaS TA using the SPIRS TEE SDK—demonstrating how a RISC-V-based TEE can be used to create a secure external entropy service for a fleet of IoT devices.

2 Background

Entropy generates the desired randomness for security services. In practice, this randomness must be generated artificially. Achieving true randomness can be challenging and requires careful design. The aim of this research is to identify a solution to provide true entropy for a fleet of IoT devices that lack the resources to generate it themselves.

RISC-V is a reduced instruction set computer (RISC) architecture that is used to develop custom processors for many different purposes. TEE hardware is a high-level security solution to create a secure area for the central processing unit (CPU). This isolated security area aims to assure confidentiality and integrity. To achieve the aim of this research, RISC-V and TEE are both used within SPIRS. The SPIRS project is introduced more thoroughly in [Section 2.1](#), [Section 2.2](#), and [Section 2.3](#).

2.1 Hardware: SPIRS Platform

The SPIRS [20] EU-funded project addresses innovative approaches to provide security and data privacy to Information and Communications Technology (ICT) elements. The project encompasses the complete design of a SPIRS platform, which integrates a dedicated hardware Root of Trust (RoT), a RISC-V processor core, and some peripherals. The SPIRS hardware platform ([Figure 1](#)) includes three components:

CORE-V CVA6 Core: The RISC-V processor in SPIRS is based on the open-source CORE-V CVA6 core, developed by the OpenHW group. The SPIRS project enhances the security of this core by addressing vulnerabilities identified in the PP84 protection profile of the Common Criteria [4]. Security countermeasures have been applied to ensure the processor operates securely, even in untrusted environments.

RoT: The RoT is the foundational security element of the SPIRS platform, as it is the source of trust for the entire system built over it. The security of software components (execution environment, boot process, applications) relies on identifiers, random numbers, and cryptographic functions that are provided by the RoT. The RoT is modular and flexible, allowing for the addition or removal of components to optimize the system for specific applications. This flexibility ensures that the platform can adapt to new security threats by updating its RoT. The current version of the hardware RoT includes:

Physical Unclonable Function (PUF)/TRNG: A hardware-based mechanism, based on a Ring Oscillator architecture, which generates unique identifiers and random numbers for device authentication and security operations.

AES-256: A symmetric encryption engine for securing data.

SHA-256: A cryptographic hashing function used to ensure data integrity.

Digital Signatures: A hardware implementation of algorithms to accelerate and secure digital authentication.

Peripherals: A collection of peripherals enables various use cases using the SPIRS platform.

In addition to DDR3 memory, the platform includes Ethernet, UART, SPI, JTAG, Boot ROM, PLIC, and CLINT.

Fig. 1: SPIRS Hardware Platform

Prototype Platform Implementation. A prototype of the SPIRS platform integrates the above components, and demonstrates secure communication between the RISC-V processor, the RoT, and the High-Level Operating System (HLOS), mediated by the TEE.

To speed up and facilitate development, the SPIRS TEE SDK also includes a preconfigured virtualized environment, based on QEMU.

2.2 SPIRS TEE Platform

The TEE is a crucial element of the SPIRS platform. It enables secure execution of critical operations, isolating the trusted codebase from potentially compromised or untrusted components. Figure 2 visually summarizes the main components of the SPIRS TEE architecture and their interactions. The rest of this section, and the following one, provide more details about these components and how different actors interact with the SPIRS platform.

At the core of the TEE design is the **Security Monitor (SM)**, which has the highest execution privilege on the platform. The SM manages memory and device access, using Physical Memory Protection (PMP) [2, Section 3.7] for compartmentalization and leveraging the hardware RoT to ensure security. The SM also mediates communication between **TAs** running in the TEE and untrusted components, such as userspace **Client Applications (CAs)** within the HLOS.

Fig. 2: Basic SPIRS TEE stack

TAs are lightweight applications running within the TEE, with minimal permissions to reduce the attack surface. These applications rely on the **SPIRS Trusted Runtime** for accessing RoT services and basic functionalities like memory management.

2.3 Software: SPIRS-TEE-SDK

The SPIRS TEE SDK simplifies the development, testing, and deployment of applications leveraging the SPIRS TEE. It is built upon a fork of the open-source Keystone framework [12], tailored specifically for RISC-V hardware platforms.

The SDK defines pairs of applications: CAs executing in the untrusted environment, and TAs running securely within the TEE. Communication between TAs and userspace CAs is mediated through dedicated **TEE Client** (`tee_client_api`) and internal (`tee_internal_api`) libraries, based on the GlobalPlatform (GP) TEE specifications [8, 6, 7].

Briefly, the typical workflow, depicted in Figure 3 and detailed below, involves writing application logic for both the CA and TA, configuring build parameters (such as `APP_NAME` and a unique `TA_UUID`), and compiling them alongside the SPIRS Trusted Runtime into a single executable Keystone application package (`.ke`).

Figure 3 comprehensively depicts the different phases of a typical workflow when using the SPIRS TEE SDK:

Fig. 3: SPIRS TEE SDK Workflow

Provisioning: The vendor of the SPIRS platform can provision specific boards, based on a description of the platform configuration **1**. This is processed by the SPIRS fork of Keystone, augmented with further tweaks provided by the SPIRS SDK, to generate **2** a trusted SM binary and a platform manifest, which embeds an SM manifest authenticating the binary, together with a public key and a specification related to the platform. Furthermore, this step is also used to initialize the SDK environment for development.

Development: Once the SDK environment is provisioned, developers can implement and maintain, for each of their TAs, the code base **4** for the TA/CA pair, alongside the configuration tuning the enclave which will be spawned to run a specific TA in the SPIRS TEE (e.g., configuring memory boundaries and access to resources and peripherals, an APP_NAME and a unique TA_UUID). These will be processed through the SPIRS fork of Keystone, enhanced by tweaks and APIs provided by the SPIRS SDK, to generate **5** executable binary artifacts for the CA and a single executable Keystone application package (`.ke`), which conveniently collects the TA binary artifact,

the SPIRS Trusted Loader, the SPIRS Trusted Runtime (based on the Keystone Trusted Runtime *Eyrie*), and a manifest authenticating the bundle. The SDK facilitates rapid prototyping and testing via integration with the QEMU virtualized environment, offering a practical alternative to physical hardware during early development stages.

Additional capabilities include straightforward integration of third-party libraries via static linking, streamlined environment setup through provided scripts, and automated test execution within QEMU.

Deployment: The operator of the platform can install the SPIRS board where needed. They deploy on its storage, the SM binary output ② obtained through the *Provisioning*, their choice of a supported Linux kernel and filesystem (the SDK provisioning also produces these, although operators can optionally ship a different one, as needed), and on top of the filesystem they also install the *Development* artifacts ⑤ for the CA and the executable Keystone application package.

At boot, the board uses the provisioned public key to authenticate the SM binary, before loading and executing it in memory ③ to continue the Secure Boot process: the Linux kernel and filesystem are hashed before loading, and their values saved in dedicated security registers. The Linux Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) subsystem can read those values, and use additional security registers to record the digests of further loaded components.

Once boot is completed, a kernel driver allows userspace to interact with the SM to spawn an isolated TEE enclave ⑦ to run the TA from the executable Keystone application package (*.ke*), as well as the associated CA ⑥ in the *Untrusted* HLOS to interact with it.

Attestation: Finally, a Remote Attestation protocol ⑧ based on Challenge/Response, allows a Remote Verifier to attest the authenticity of the hardware and software components of the platform, based on the Platform and TA manifests generated in *Provisioning* and *Development*. The attestation report can also leverage the Linux IMA subsystem and the secure registers, to let the SM generate a signed quote covering all the measured components.

The Remote Attestation mechanism integrated within the SPIRS TEE SDK extends the security properties of the established communication channels. On top of the confidentiality provided by protocols such as Transport Layer Security (TLS), upon successful completion of the Remote Attestation protocol, the communicating parties additionally gain *mutual authentication*, guaranteeing that each party's identity has been securely verified; *integrity*, ensuring not only the exchanged data but also the software state of the attested platform have not been tampered with, as well as proof of a genuine hardware configuration; and *freshness*, confirming that the attestation data reflects the current state rather than a replayed past state.

These extra security guarantees significantly reduce the threat surface protecting the communication channel against impersonation, replay, and tampering attacks, ultimately enhancing trust in the remotely attested execution environments.

3 Use case: Entropy and IoT

True randomness, or entropy—a reliable measure of randomness—can be achieved with methods that can generate actual random data. This entropy is hard to achieve as it is not straightforward to identify methods for gathering truly random inputs or generating truly random data using specific input sources. The introduction describes a variety of previous methods for achieving entropy. However, these methods can call true randomness into question if the methods or inputs follow a pattern or the data can be manipulated.

Methods used for generating true randomness are known as TRNGs. TRNGs include, but are not limited to, chaos [21], electrical noise [21], free-running oscillators [21], quantum effects [21], and radioactive decay [23]. Chaos is addressed using methods like biosignals [3], multi-dimensional chaotic systems [5], and wind flow [10]. To explain further, radioactive decay is used to retrieve random signals to support creating true randomness [23]. TRNGs based on Ring Oscillators are a recent and well-known technique for achieving entropy in IoT systems [18].

In addition to TRNGs that use true randomness, there are also Pseudo-random Number Generators (PRNGs) which are algorithms that transform input seed values into longer and uniformly distributed deterministic bit streams, meaning that the same seed value will always result in the same output value. In order for a PRNG to be considered a Cryptographically Secure Pseudorandom Number Generator (CSPRNG), it must provide both forward and backward unpredictability.

Because of their limited resources, constrained IoT devices may encounter difficulty in producing the strong entropy necessary for cryptographically secure random numbers [9]. Furthermore, Petro and Cecil [17] identify numerous additional security issues with IoT Random Number Generators (RNGs), including (i) Lack of access to proper CSPRNG subsystems due to lack of modern OS; (ii) Developers frequently making incorrect calls to hardware TRNGs; (iii) The difficulty of handling hardware TRNG errors correctly; (iv) Inadequate documentation for bare-metal function calls; and (v) Flaws in the entropy distillation process that generate subpar quality hardware TRNG.

A way to solve the problem of limited entropy for IoT devices is to use EaaS [14], first introduced by Vassilev and Staples in 2016 [22]. In contrast to *Randomness Beacons* [13], in an EaaS system, a server only distributes secure and fresh entropy to clients that specifically request it, instead of broadcasting it in timed intervals. Previous research demonstrated that TEE offers security for diverse applications, and we are now broadening this research domain by introducing an external entropy provision service [16]. The entropy received from an EaaS server with secure TEE hardware is inherently suitable for cryptographic use, unlike the publicly known entropy provided by the more-researched *Randomness Beacons*.

4 EaaS Design

Our EaaS solution consists of three main components: (i) an IoT client; (ii) a Trusted Execution Server (TES); and (iii) entropy sources. The high-level idea is that a resource-constrained IoT device sends a Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) request to a server, which subsequently processes the request by fetching fresh entropy from the entropy sources, generates strong entropy by combining the entropy received from the entropy sources, and finally transmits the entropy to the IoT client. The protocol incorporates a verification function that validates both the digital signature generated by the TES and the freshness of the received entropy.

We employ a fleet of IoT devices in our implementation, each of which has a limited capacity to generate entropy. However, none of them has sufficient resources to independently generate strong and crypto-secure entropy. Thus, the IoT client is represented by one of the IoT devices in the fleet, while the remaining devices serve as the entropy sources.

Because the entropy fetching and generation portion of the protocol is executed within a TEE, the trust is placed in the TEE technology rather than a third-party entity (server operator). Thus, we refer to this server as a TES instead of a TTP server.

In order to use asymmetric encryption, we assume a key provisioning model which gets rid of the chicken-and-egg problem; i.e., we assume that the manufacturer has provided a strong initial key to the IoT client. Thus, the IoT client does not need to use EaaS for generating the strong key required for using the EaaS system in the first place. Additionally, we assume that the IoT client has previously obtained the public key of the TES (pk_{TES}).

When the IoT client wants to request entropy from the TES, it first generates a timestamp (t_1) and then sends a self-signed request to the TES that has been encrypted with the public key of the TES (pk_{TES}). The encrypted request contains the public key (pk_{IoT}), the quantity of entropy requested (ΔS), and a digital signature (σ_1).

After the TES receives the request, it fetches an amount ΔS of entropy from the entropy sources (denoted by ΔS_1 and ΔS_2), and then combines the entropy (denoted by S) and generates a timestamp (t_2). TES also creates a fixed-length symmetric session key ($sk_{session}$). To distribute the symmetric key to the IoT client, the TES encrypts the symmetric key $sk_{session}$ with the public key of the IoT client pk_{IoT} . This symmetric key $sk_{session}$ is used to encrypt the encapsulated message that contains both the generated entropy S and the timestamp t_2 . Finally, TES signs both the encrypted symmetric session key and the encapsulated message with its secret key (sk_{TES}). The result is a digital signature (σ_2).

The response from TES to the IoT client is thus a message that contains: (i) a fixed-length symmetric session key $sk_{session}$, encrypted with the public key of the IoT client pk_{IoT} ; (ii) an encapsulated response to the request for entropy. This response contains the generated entropy S and the timestamp t_2 and is

Fig. 4: EaaS Protocol

encrypted with the fixed-length symmetric session key $sk_{session}$; (iii) a digital signature σ_2 , signed with the secret key of TES sk_{TES} .

After decrypting the message, the IoT client verifies that: (i) the message contains the requested entropy S with the requested amount of entropy ΔS , the digital signature σ_2 , and the timestamp of the entropy generation t_2 ; (ii) the freshness of the generated entropy ($t_2 > t_1$); and (iii) the digital signature σ_2 is valid. The protocol is depicted in Figure 4.

4.1 Security considerations and evaluations

TEE provides security even if the server operator is malicious. The TEE technology ensures the security of the EaaS system, even in the event of a malicious server operator, provided it functions properly. This justifies calling the server a TES rather than a TTP server. Side-channel attacks are a potential attack vector against the TEE technology that may undermine the security assumptions. While we are currently unaware of any side-channel attacks against the RISC-V-based TEE we use in our EaaS implementation, it is important to be aware of this potential attack vector.

Self-signing the request for entropy protects against a malicious actor on the communication link. We assume that there is a malicious actor on the link or that the link may have some corruption. Self-signing the request with the IoT device’s private key binds the public and private keys, as well as the entropy quantity request for the transaction. Similar self-signing is used in Public-Key Infrastructure (PKI) with a Certificate Signing Request to certify a public key by a Certificate Authority. Without this self-signing, a malicious actor could perform a simple Denial of Service (DoS) attack by modifying the public key, preventing the requester from decrypting the response. Additionally, the malicious actor could alter the quantity of requested entropy, resulting in insufficient entropy for the requesting IoT client. Of course, a malicious actor

can simply drop messages, but this only affects the requester. If the message is returned and rejected by the requester, it is likely that they will request it again. This could impact the TES, either by keeping it busy servicing constant messages or, in the worst-case scenario, by depleting the entropy source, which can affect all IoT nodes.

Throttling requests from a single source stops the depletion of entropy. To avoid entropy depletion, we use a throttling mechanism on the TES to limit the number of requests from a single source. This protects the EaaS system from a bad actor who repeatedly makes valid requests to the TES with the goal of consuming all entropy. In addition to malicious actors, this will also offer protection against misconfigured or buggy networks/devices that repeatedly request entropy for non-malicious reasons. An alternative solution to fixing this problem would be to assume that the initial factory provisioning provides not only a key-pair but also a certificate that can be verified by the TES. However, this approach adds more overhead to the protocol and may not even be feasible on these constrained IoT devices. Thus, we instead implement a throttling mechanism.

A symmetric session key is used for encrypting the TES response because of public key encryption data size limitations. The payload size for public key encryption is limited. For example, RSA can only perform one encryption step, which means it can only encrypt data up to the key size minus padding and header data. After removing padding, header data, timestamp, and signature data from our TES response, we are left with the data size available for the actual entropy payload. This means that either the requested amount of entropy must be less than this amount, or the protocol must support multiple messages in order to return all of the requested entropy in case the requested amount exceeds the available data size. Thus, to avoid unnecessary protocol overhead, we use fixed-length symmetric session keys to encrypt the TES response payload.

5 Software implementation

We implemented our EaaS solution using the SPIRS TEE SDK with the QEMU virtualized environment. The software implementation was developed and tested on an Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS machine. We used the QEMU platform instead of actual SPIRS hardware due to the ease of implementation and speed of development. The QEMU platform contains a RISC-V virtual machine image that includes bootloaders, SM, Linux kernel, and rootfs.

To provide developers with easy access to cryptographic functions, we used OpenSSL as a third-party library. In order to get the third-party library to work, we built a static OpenSSL library with a RISC-V musl toolchain and added it to the SPIRS TEE SDK build process.

We used a minimal Trusted Computing Base (TCB) design, running only the necessary components inside the TEE enclave (TA). In practice, only the

code for obtaining and combining entropy, generating the keys, computing and verifying the digital signatures, and encrypting and decrypting the messages is run inside a TA. The rest of the code is executed on the CA.

Network Time Protocol (NTP) is used for timestamps. AES-128 is used for symmetric encryption and RSA-3072 is used for asymmetric encryption. We use a hybrid scheme: RSA-3072 for signatures and AES-128 for payload encryption.

The EaaS demo application serves as a functional Proof-of-Concept illustrating that the SPIRS TEE SDK is suitable for the practical development of useful TAs.

5.1 Limitations

A limitation of our work is that we are only using entropy gathered from the entropy sources, which in our case are the IoT devices in the fleet, all of which are based on the PUF/TRNG inside the hardware RoT of SPIRS devices. Therefore, any potential flaws with this PUF/TRNG implementation would also directly affect the quality of entropy generated by our EaaS system. To address this problem, our EaaS implementation could be modified to also use other trusted entropy sources. We recommend that real-world EaaS implementations use many trusted entropy sources that are based on different phenomena, so that any potential flaws in one method do not invalidate the quality of generated entropy. Since our EaaS design allows the easy addition of entropy sources, this is easily achievable in any real-world implementation based on our design.

The development happened on a virtualized QEMU environment instead of the actual SPIRS hardware. To get the software working on the actual SPIRS hardware, we would need to develop further mappings between the OpenSSL library and the trusted hardware implementations. However, since the cryptographic functions used in the software implementation are mostly the same functions that are supported by the trusted hardware components of the SPIRS TEE hardware platform, this should be straightforward to achieve. Future research should include hardware and performance benchmarking to assess the practicality and usability of our solution.

Our implementation relies on a single TES, creating a potential single point of failure. However, our design could be easily extended to include features such as load balancing for high availability in production environments where a single point of failure is not acceptable. The design could also be extended for a decentralized solution.

The threats posed by a future Cryptographically Relevant Quantum Computer (CRQC) inherently affect this project as well. In this work, we did not directly address Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) concerns, as the efforts for the PQC transition are orthogonal to our application. Nonetheless, it is worth remarking that as both confidentiality and authentication based on asymmetric cryptography are impacted by the quantum threats, real-world deployments of this work should select Post-Quantum/Traditional (PQ/T) hybrid algorithms to secure the communication channels against attacks such as Harvest-Now-Decrypt-Later (HNDL). While threats to authentication do require an active

attacker with access to a CRQC, the direct threat here does not need to be addressed as urgently as asymmetric encryption. Nonetheless, as we are well aware of the many challenges in any migration affecting the PKI, we remark on the urgency to address the PQC transition of the PKI to provide a sustainable migration path for devices and applications such as the ones described here. Finally, on a related note, we recognize that one limitation of the current implementation of the SPIRS platform is that its RoT does not embed support for PQC primitives: a natural evolution for the SPIRS project would consist in providing support in hardware and firmware to establish a chain of trust based on PQ/T hybrid algorithms.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a working EaaS demo application and its design that utilizes the SPIRS TEE SDK, demonstrating that developing useful TAs for an open-source RISC-V-based TEE is both feasible and effective. Our implementation highlights the potential of combining open hardware with secure software to address real-world challenges in IoT security.

EaaS warrants further research. Our work showcases that designing and building a working EaaS implementation is practical and useful for IoT devices that lack sufficient resources to generate strong entropy by themselves. However, there is limited scientific research and practical applications for EaaS, as most of the attention seems to be on the somewhat-related Randomness Beacons. We believe our implementation illustrates that EaaS, particularly when backed by a TEE for a TES, offers distinct advantages in selective entropy delivery, remote attestation, and system scalability. EaaS ensures confidentiality, freshness, and trust in entropy distribution—making it a compelling direction for both academic inquiry and industrial adoption. We encourage future work to explore alternative entropy sources, multi-tenant TES infrastructures, and deployment in heterogeneous hardware ecosystems.

The SPIRS TEE SDK allows practical development of TAs for open-source RISC-V hardware. Our EaaS demo application demonstrates that the SPIRS TEE SDK enables practical development of TAs for the RISC-V-based SPIRS hardware platform. This application is a meaningful demonstration of how TAs can be developed on open-source RISC-V-based TEE hardware. The open-source toolchain, support for virtualization via QEMU, and integration of cryptographic primitives through trusted runtime components make the SDK suitable for rapid prototyping and academic experimentation. We anticipate that the SPIRS platform and SDK will lower the barrier to entry for developing new TAs in diverse domains, including embedded security, supply chain attestation, and privacy-preserving analytics.

Our design warrants benchmarking and comparison with other solutions. This paper presents our EaaS design and its simple QEMU-based implementation. The scope did not include performance or hardware measurements.

Future research should measure the overhead of the EaaS implementation and evaluate its scalability for multiple concurrent IoT clients. Additionally, we recommend comparing our solution to other EaaS and Randomness Beacon systems.

7 Code availability

As we fully support Open Science principles, we have published our code with an open-source (MIT) license. The code can be accessed through the following Git repository: <https://gitlab.com/nisec/spirs-tee-sdk-eaastee-public-fork>. The Git repository includes a detailed *README.md* file with a tutorial for using the SPIRS TEE SDK as well as running our demo EaaS application. The *README.md* file also explains the chosen algorithms and design choices in further detail.

8 Authorship Contributions

J.N., A.A., N.T., and B.M. acquired funding.
 A.P. led the article writing and administration.
 A.C.A. and N.T. designed the RISC-V SPIRS SDK.
 A.P. and J.N. designed the entropy provision service.
 J.S. analyzed the entropy provision protocol.
 A.A., N.T., and B.M. validated and verified our work.
 M.K. contributed to the visualization of diagrams.
 A.P., J.N., and B.M. proofread the manuscript.
 B.M., A.P., and J.N. edited the final version of the paper.
 Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) statement of authorship contribution.

Contributions	A.P.	J.N.	A.C.A.	N.T.	J.S.	M.K.	B.M.
Data curation	●	○	○	○	○	○	○
Formal Analysis	●	○	○	●	○	○	○
Funding acquisition	○	●	●	●	○	○	●
Investigation	●	●	○	●	●	○	○
Methodology	●	●	○	●	●	○	●
Project administration	●	●	●	○	○	○	○
Resources	○	○	●	○	○	○	○
Software	●	●	●	●	○	○	○
Supervision	●	●	●	○	○	○	○
Validation	○	○	○	●	○	○	○
Visualization	●	●	●	●	○	●	○
Writing—original draft	●	●	●	●	●	○	○
Writing—review & editing	●	●	○	○	○	○	●

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